

Improved ionic conductivity of $\text{Na}_{3.2+2x}\text{Mg}_x\text{Zr}_{2-x}\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$) solid electrolyte by microwave sintering

Kwang Myong Choea, Jong Sung Paka, Myong Hyok Kima

Faculty of Chemical Engineering, Kim Chaek University of Technology, Pyongyang, DPR Korea

Abstract - In this paper, we prepared Mg-doped sodium superionic conductors $\text{Na}_{3.2+2x}\text{Mg}_x\text{Zr}_{2-x}\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$) by solid state synthesis and investigated the effect of microwave sintering on their ionic conductivity. Sintering was carried out at 1100 °C for 1 h using a 2.45 GHz microwave sintering furnace, and the phase composition, microstructure, density and ionic conductivity were compared with those of the samples sintered at 1250 °C for 5 h in conventional sintering method. XRD analysis showed that the main phase in microwave sintered samples was a monoclinic C2/c NASICON phase for $x \leq 0.05$, and a rhombohedral crystalline R3c NASICON phase for $x > 0.05$. There also existed a secondary phase, the Mg-doped Na_3PO_4 phase, though weak. The maximum ionic conductivity at room temperature for microwave sintered samples was found to be 3.86 mS cm⁻¹ for the sample with a composition of $\text{Na}_{3.3}\text{Mg}_{0.05}\text{Zr}_{1.95}\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$, which was improved by about 37% compared to the maximum ionic conductivity of 2.82 mS cm⁻¹ for the sample with a composition of $\text{Na}_{3.35}\text{Mg}_{0.075}\text{Zr}_{1.925}\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$ in the conventional sintering mode.

Keywords - Solid state synthesis, NASICON, Microwave sintering, ionic conductivity, solid electrolyte.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lithium ion batteries are now widely used worldwide due to their high energy density. However, there are disadvantages such as high cost, explosion risk and leakage risk due to the use of liquid electrolytes consisting of conducting salts and organic solvents. Also, the depletion of lithium resources limits mass production. It is of a great importance to develop a low-cost, stable, environment-friendly and all-solid-state sodium ion battery. Herein, one of the important problems is to develop solid electrolytes with a high sodium ionic conductivity.

The most remarkable material is the sodium superionic conductor (NASICON) solid electrolyte. In 1976, NASICON-type compounds with a general formula of $\text{Na}_{1+x}\text{Zr}_2\text{Si}_x\text{P}_{3-x}\text{O}_{12}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 3$) (NZSP) were first proposed by H.Y.P. Hong [1] and J.B. Goodenough [2]. Since then, besides conventional sintering [3-8], several sintering techniques such as hot pressure sintering [9], spark plasma sintering [10], cold sintering [11] have been investigated to

enhance the ionic conductivity of NZSP by increasing the density of the samples and improving the grain boundary properties. However, some sintering methods have not been widely used due to strict equipment requirements, and some have not made a significant progress in enhancement of ionic conductivity of NZSP due to the uneven temperature distribution during sintering. Recently, a microwave sintering method was reported to enhance the ionic conductivity of NZSP [12].

There are several reports available to enhance the ionic conductivity by substitution of Zr^{4+} in NZSP thus widening the sodium ion transport pathways and increasing the sodium ion concentration: Zr^{4+} was, in detail, substituted with divalent cations such as Ca^{2+} [14, 23], Co^{2+} [14], Ni^{2+} [13, 14], Zn^{2+} [14, 24], trivalent cations such as Sc^{3+} [16, 25-30], Fe^{3+} [31], Y^{3+} [24, 31, 32], La^{3+} [32, 33], Nd^{3+} [32], Gd^{3+} [34], Yb^{3+} [34], tetravalent cations such as Hf^{4+} [16] and pentavalent cations such as Nb^{5+} [24, 35]. Moreover, the doping of various elements, including rare earth elements, enhanced the ionic conductivity [36-43]. However, some of the

elements were not widely used due to their high cost, while there was no significant improvement of the ionic conductivity for other elements compared to the original NZSP. T. Takahashi et al. [22] used low-cost and efficient Mg^{2+} as an additive cation of NZSP for the first time. Since then, many studies have been reported to enhance the ionic conductivity by Mg^{2+} doping in NZSP prepared in various methods [11, 13-21]. H. Leng et al. [11] prepared $Na_{3.256}Mg_{0.128}Zr_{1.872}Si_2PO_{12}$ with a relative density of about 93% and ionic conductivity of $1.36 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ by cold sintering, while Q. Zhang et al. [15] prepared $Na_{3.3}Zr_{1.85}Mg_{0.15}Si_2PO_{12}$ with ionic conductivity of $3.54 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°C by conventional sintering method. J. Wang et al. [20] improved the ionic conductivity by doping Mg^{2+} in the Zr^{4+} -position of NZSP, where the resulting phase was the rhombohedral R3c phase and the maximum ionic conductivity at room temperature was found to be $2.4 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at $x=0.25$ for $Na_{3+x}Zr_{2-x}Si_2PO_{12}$. Recently, there has been reported the enhancement of ionic conductivity by changing the Si/P value to 2.2/0.8 for Mg^{2+} doped NZSP [18,19].

M. Samiee et al. [13] carried out a detailed study on the mechanism of the ionic conductivity enhancement for Mg-doped NZSP. The effect of dopant elements on the bulk and grain boundary ionic conductivity in NZSP was investigated through experiments and calculations, and it was found that Mg^{2+} was dissolved in the secondary phase produced at grain boundaries, rather than substituted in the framework structure in the bulk phase, thereby inhibiting the formation of the secondary phase with a low ionic conductivity and increasing ionic conductivity by producing the conductive secondary phase.

It was also found that the ionic conductivity increased with increasing Si/P ratio in the primary bulk phase, but beyond a limited range, the ionic conductivity decreased due to the transition from monoclinic to rhombohedral with lower ionic conductivity, and hence the highest Si/P values (2.2/0.8) within the monoclinic range exhibited the highest ionic conductivity. The Mg content for the maximum ionic conductivity was lower for $Na_{3.2}Zr_2Si_2.2P_{0.8}O_{12}$ (NZSP2.2) with Si/P value of

2.2/0.8 than for NZSP with Si/P value of 2/1, indicating that the Si/P value of 2.2/0.8 was associated with a lower content of the produced secondary phase Na_3PO_4 and thus a lower content of soluble Mg due to the low P content in the primary bulk phase. In NZSP2.2, the maximum ionic conductivity of $2.7 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ was found at $x=0.0625$, while in NZSP 2.05 $\text{mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at $x=0.125$.

There are, however, few reports available which NASICON phase with higher ionic conductivity in the primary bulk phase is. Many studies have reported that the monoclinic NASICON C2/c phase has higher ionic conductivity than the rhombohedral NASICON R3c phase, whereas some studies [20] have reported that the rhombohedral R3c phase is higher than the monoclinic C2/c phase. Moreover, for the same Si/P value, there were reported various contents of Mg doping for the maximum ionic conductivity. There has been a report on the conventional sintering conditions on ionic conductivity [44].

It has also been reported that microwave sintering could achieve a uniform and fast heating rate due to the interaction between microwave and material at the micro-level, which would reduce the sintering temperature, shorten the sintering time, and improve the ionic conductivity in the preparation of NZSP by homogenizing the particles [12]. However, there are few reports available on the enhancement of ionic conductivity and the mechanism for the use of microwave sintering in the Mg-doped NASICON material.

Hence, in this work, we prepared $Na_{3.2+2x}Mg_xZr_{2-x}Si_2.2P_{0.8}O_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$) at 1100°C for 1 h using microwave sintering and investigated the effect of microwave sintering on the ionic conductivity of Mg doped NZSP2.2 compared with samples sintered at 1250°C for 5 h by conventional sintering method.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation

The samples of $Na_{3.2+2x}Zr_{2-x}Mg_xSi_2.2P_{0.8}O_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$) were

prepared using microwave sintering. The raw materials were Na_2CO_3 ($\geq 99.8\%$), $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ ($\geq 99\%$), SiO_2 ($\geq 99.9\%$), MgO ($\geq 99.99\%$) and ZrO_2 ($\geq 99.99\%$). First, the raw materials were taken as stoichiometric and wet-milled for 12 h at 400 rpm using anhydrous ethanol as the medium in a planetary ball mill.

The solvent was evaporated, and the dried powder was calcined at 1 000 °C for 10 h using a muffle furnace in an alumina crucible. The sintered powder was then ball milled again (the grinding conditions were the same as before) and unidirectional compacting was carried out in a pellet form with a diameter of 14 mm and a height of 4 mm under a pressure of 20MPa. The pellet was then sintered at 1100 °C for 1 h at a heating rate of 30 °C/min in a 2.45 GHz microwave furnace. For comparison, another pellet of the same composition was sintered at 1 250 °C for 5 h at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in the conventional method. Hereafter, NMZSPmw would refer to samples sintered by microwave sintering method, while NMZSPconv refer to samples sintered by the conventional method. Table 1 lists their various versions with respect to Mg content (that is x value).

Table 1. Abbreviations of $\text{Na}_{3.2+2x}\text{Mg}_x\text{Zr}_{2-x}\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$ ($x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$) sintered samples according to Mg content and sintering mode

Mg content (x value)	Sintering mode	
	Microwave sintering	Conventional sintering
0	NMZSP _{mw} -0	NMZSP _{conv} -0
0.025	NMZSP _{mw} - 0.025	NMZSP _{conv} - 0.025
0.05	NMZSP _{mw} - 0.05	NMZSP _{conv} - 0.05
0.075	NMZSP _{mw} - 0.075	NMZSP _{conv} - 0.075
0.1	NMZSP _{mw} -0.1	NMZSP _{conv} -0.1

Characterization

The sintered densities of all the samples were measured using the water penetration technique based on the Archimedes principle. The phase composition analysis of all the sintered samples was characterized by an X-ray diffraction analyzer (D8ADVANCE). Microstructures of NMZSPmw-0.05 and NMZSPconv-0.05 samples were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (JSM-6610A). The grain size was determined by SEM image analysis. The ionic conductivity of the sintered samples was determined using an AC impedance spectrum measured by an Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (Metrohm Autolab EIS) at room temperature.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phase composition

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show the results of the phase composition analysis by X-ray diffraction of samples sintered in both microwave and conventional sintering methods. For the microwave sintered samples (Fig. 1 (a)-(c)) the monoclinic NASICON phase with C2/c space group was formed for $x \leq 0.05$ and then the rhombohedral NASICON phase with R3c space group for $x > 0.05$.

The formation of cubic Na_3PO_4 phase with an impurity phase was observed around 21 °, with peak intensity exhibiting an increasing trend with Mg concentration (Fig. 1(d)). ZrO_2 phase, the main impurity phase, was not observed, which might be attributed to a high Si content and a subsequent low solubility of ZrO_2 thus inhibiting the formation of ZrO_2 , due to a Si/P value of 2.2/0.8 in $\text{Na}_{3.2+2x}\text{Zr}_{2-x}\text{Mg}_x\text{Si}_{2.2}\text{P}_{0.8}\text{O}_{12}$ samples. Also, it might come from a decrease in Zr content due to addition of Mg as well as a low sintering temperature and a short sintering time. M. Samiee et al. reported that, with increasing Mg content, the NASICON phase was converted from monoclinic with C2/c space groups to rhombohedral with R3c space groups [13]. In our study, the rhombohedral R3c phase was present when the x values were 0.075 and 0.1 for the microwave sintered samples. The NMZSPconv samples sintered in the conventional method for comparison, however, exhibited only the monoclinic C2/c phase as the main phase, which could be

attributed to our Si/P ratio of 2.2/0.8 and the relatively low amount of Na₃PO₄ produced that might limit the adding amount of Mg to <0.1. (Fig. 2 (a)-(c)) In addition, with the Na₃PO₄ phase (Fig. 2(d)), the weak ZrO₂ phase was identified as the impurity phase (Fig. 2(e)). This could be because of the high sintering temperature and relatively long sintering time in the conventional sintering method. In the conventional method, the peak of Na₃PO₄ phase also exhibited an increasing tendency with Mg content (Fig. 2(d)). This could be mainly related to the dissolution of the added Mg into the secondary phase Na₃PO₄, which is consistent with M. Samiee's report [13].

Figure 1. (a) XRD patterns of NMZSPmw-x (x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1), (b-d) are high-magnification patterns of selected areas

Figure 2. (a) XRD patterns of NMZSPconv-x (x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1), (b-e) are high-magnification patterns of selected areas

Microstructure

Fig. 3 shows the SEM images of the NMZSPmw-0.05 and NMZSPconv-0.05 sintered samples. In Fig. 3(a), all spherical parts are monoclinic C2/c NASICON phase, while short fibrous parts are attributed to Mg-doped Na₃PO₄ phase.

The bright small spherical parts that only exist in the conventionally sintered sample might be attributed to the generation of ZrO₂ phase. (Fig. 3(b)) The microwave-sintered sample showed less porosity than the conventionally sintered sample. This could be due to the high temperature during conventional sintering, which is responsible for the volatilization of some of the volatile Na and P components at high temperature. Moreover, the microwave sintered sample had an average grain size of about 2 μm for the primary bulk phase, whereas the conventional sintered sample had a large average grain size of about 5 μm with nonuniform distribution. This might be because of more uniform temperature distribution and higher thermal efficiency in microwave sintering compared to conventional sintering.

Figure 3. SEM images of (a) NMZSPmw-0.05 and (b) NMZSPconv-0.05

Density measurement

The densities of all the sintered samples were measured by water impregnation technique based on Archimedes principle (Table 2).

Table 2. Densities of samples with different Mg contents sintered by microwave sintering and conventional sintering methods

NMZSP _{mw} - x (x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1)samples	density, g·cm ⁻³	NMZSP _{conv} - x (x=0, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1)samples	density, g·cm ⁻³
NMZSP _{mw} - 0	3.21	NMZSP _{conv} - 0	3.08

NMZSP _{mw} -0.025	3.18	NMZSP _{conv} -0.025	3.05
NMZSP _{mw} -0.05	3.16	NMZSP _{conv} -0.05	3.02
NMZSP _{mw} -0.075	3.14	NMZSP _{conv} -0.075	3.00
NMZSP _{mw} -0.1	3.11	NMZSP _{conv} -0.1	2.98

The density values of the microwave-sintered samples were increased by about 4.5% on average than the conventionally sintered samples. Since microwave sintering is a thermal sintering process that occurs due to the interaction of microwave and NASICON materials, it shows a much better sintering performance compared to the conventional sintering method, thus making itself a preferable choice for preparing dense NASICON samples. Moreover, the sintering density tends to decrease with increasing Mg content in both of the sintering methods, which might be attributed to an increase in size due to modifying the framework structure by dissolving Mg in the primary and secondary phases within a limited range.

Ionic conductivity

The ionic conductivity of the samples sintered in microwave and conventional sintering methods was obtained by EIS. For precise analysis, both sides of the sintered samples were polished with silicon carbide abrasive paper and silver paste was coated onto both sides of the samples. The total ionic conductivity of the solid electrolyte was calculated by the following equation [45].

$$\sigma_{tot} = \frac{h}{A(R_b + R_{gb})}$$

In the equation, h , A , R_b , R_{gb} are the thickness[cm] of the pellet, surface area of the specimen [cm²], R_b the bulk resistance [Ω], and R_{gb} the grain boundary resistance [Ω], respectively. Figs. 4 and 5 show the

Nyquist plots of the microwave-sintered and conventionally sintered samples.

Figure 4. Nyquist plots of NMZSP_{mw}-x (x=0,0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1)

Figure 5. Nyquist plots of NMZSP_{conv}-x (x=0,0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1)

The obtained plots exhibit a distorted arc shape. The distorted arc is a mixture of two semicircles: the first semicircle represents the bulk resistance, while the second one represents the grain boundary resistance. The bulk resistance and grain boundary resistance obtained from EIS analysis, and the total ionic conductivity calculated by Eq. 1 are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Bulk resistance, grain boundary resistance and total ionic conductivity of NMZSP_{mw-x} (x=0,0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1) and NMZSP_{conv-x} (x=0,0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1)

sample	R _b , Ω	R _{gb} , Ω	σ _{tot} , mS·cm ⁻¹	sample	R _b , Ω	R _{gb} , Ω	σ _{tot} , mS·cm ⁻¹
NMZSP _{mw} -0	24.36	51.22	3.44	NMZSP _{conv} -0	26.42	80.14	2.44
NMZSP _{mw} -0.025	23.68	47.16	3.67	NMZSP _{conv} -0.025	27.18	71.68	2.63
NMZSP _{mw} -0.05	23.57	43.78	3.86	NMZSP _{conv} -0.05	26.57	67.63	2.76
NMZSP _{mw} -0.075	22.48	48.75	3.65	NMZSP _{conv} -0.075	26.68	65.52	2.82
NMZSP _{mw} -0.1	22.39	53.63	3.42	NMZSP _{conv} -0.1	26.92	65.94	2.80

The bulk resistance almost remains unchanged with increasing Mg content in microwave sintering, and the grain boundary resistance decreases until x=0.05, and then tends to increase. It might imply that Mg has little effect on the framework structure of the primary phase. On the other hand, a decrease in grain boundary resistance with increasing x value could be due to the dissolution of Mg into the Na₃PO₄ phase produced at the grain boundary of the secondary phase, thus producing a conductive NaMgPO₄ phase. This is in good agreement with the XRD results of microwave-sintered samples. However, it starts to increase again from x = 0.05, because, due to Si/P = 2.2/0.8, the content of the Na₃PO₄ phase produced in the secondary phase is small. Hence, the amount of Mg dissolved in it was soon saturated. Thus, the extra Mg could convert the monoclinic NASICON phase into a low-conductivity rhombohedral phase in the primary bulk phase, which could be explained by the shift of the peak around 18.5-20° and 27-28°

for high Mg content in XRD analysis (Fig. 1(b, c)). However, in the conventional sintering, the ionic conductivity tends to increase with Mg content, and almost unchanged for x>0.075. This could be attributed to the higher amount of Na₃PO₄ produced due to the higher sintering temperature and longer sintering time compared to the conventional sintering method, and hence the higher concentration of Mg saturation.

In addition, the ionic conductivity of the microwave-sintered samples was higher than that of the conventionally sintered samples, because the low sintering temperature and short sintering time in microwave sintering might hinder the formation of low-conductivity ZrO₂ phase at grain boundaries. The uniform grain size distribution and high sintering density effectively might enhance the ionic conductivity in the primary and secondary phases. Also, due to the low sintering temperature and low sintering time, the evaporation of sodium ions is less than that of conventional sintering, and the total sodium ion concentration is hardly decreased thus resulting in an increase in ionic conductivity. The

maximum ionic conductivity for the microwave-sintered samples was found to be 3.86 mS-cm⁻¹ at x=0.05, which is increased by about 37% compared to 2.82 mS-cm⁻¹ at x=0.075, which is the maximum ionic conductivity for the conventionally sintered samples. This implies that microwave sintering could effectively improve the ionic conductivity of the Mg-doped NASICON material compared to conventional sintering.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, the effect of microwave sintering on the ionic conductivity of Mg-doped NZSP2.2 prepared by the solid-state method was investigated in comparison with conventional sintering. The phase composition, microstructure, density and ionic conductivity analysis showed that Mg was dissolved in the impurity phase of the grain boundary, Na₃PO₄, as in conventional sintering, to form NaMgPO₄, which enhanced the ionic conductivity under microwave sintering. Moreover, the Mg doping resulted in phase change from monoclinic to rhombohedral phase in microwave-sintered samples proceeded at x=0.05 that was lower than in conventionally sintered samples (x=0.07). The microwave sintered Mg-doped samples could be effectively used as solid electrolyte for solid sodium ion batteries, and microwave sintering may be of significance in further research to improve the ionic conductivity of NASICON doped with various elements other than Mg.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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